

The Villa delle Grotte at Grottarossa and the prehistory of Roman villas

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The origin of many Roman architectural forms continues to be debated, with a main point of contention focusing on the issue of whether Roman architectural forms were indigenous to Italy or derived from the Hellenistic world following Rome's eastward expansion. It is clear that, in aesthetic terms, Romans and Etruscans were heavily influenced by Hellenistic tendencies, often perhaps through the filter of western Greek cities such as Tarentum (Holliday 2002, 76-78). Architecture *per se*, however, poses a different dilemma since complex and developed buildings that have been found in Etruscan cities and at Rome (especially in the private sphere) predate significant contact between Rome and the Hellenistic world. By the Late Republic — precisely when the Romans had conquered the Greek East and flooded their city with Greek art and artists — the villa was a widespread building type in Central Italy. There is, however, a considerable terminological confusion, which makes any generalization about villas hard to support: buildings that have been called "villas" range in size and function from simple country houses used for farming and production to large estates often run by means of slave labour. Out of the many problems that villas still present, the one relevant here is the prehistory of this Late Republican building type, a prehistory that is far from clear but whose tendencies are much more strongly Italic than they are Hellenistic.

A further complicating factor is the scarcity of substantial architectural remains in the archaeological record of Central Italy for the 5th through 3rd c. B.C. This 'black hole' of the Middle Republic has often been interpreted as a sign of decline at Rome or, at least, of inactivity (Gros and Torelli 1988, 92-104). Recently compiled archaeological data begins to alter our perspective of this period, especially as building techniques and contemporary ceramics are better understood. The presence of monumental architecture from the Middle Republic, especially in the domestic sphere, suggests that the period was not necessarily one of decline.

Fig. 1. Map with locations of Grottarossa (A), Auditorium site (B), Tor-rino (C), Acqua Acetosa Laurentina (D) (after Quilici & Quilici Gigli 1993).

The recent discovery of the Auditorium site has made it possible to reconsider the evidence provided by a range of large sites, from Murlo and Acquarossa to the Via Gabina and Francolise sites. Grottarossa on the plateau known as the Monte delle Grotte, lying on the Via Flaminia c.9 km north of the center of Rome, also deserves to play a rôle in this new debate (fig. 1). An excavation was carried out here in March of 1926 by P. Mottini, uncovering a large villa with an unusual plan that included two *atria* and numerous rooms, along with an area seemingly associated with domestic production (fig. 2). The excavation report did not appear for almost 20 years and it was published not by Mottini but by E. Stefani, an Italian architect who was active mainly on Crete. Stefani's report (1946, 52-72) describes the excavated structure in some detail, but offers little analysis and even less in the way of chronology or comparisons. A few years later, L. Cozza (1948, 101-10) returned to the Monte delle Grotte to examine the site after roughly a third of the villa had been destroyed by a pozzolana quarry. He was able to document the system of *cuniculi* underneath the villa (fig. 3), as well as an Archaic ogive cistern connected to them (figs. 4-5). Thereafter the villa virtually disappears from the published record, apart from brief mentions in a handful of books dealing with villas in Central Italy or with the Via Flaminia. Some attempt at contextualizing the site can be found in recent discussions of Etruscan and Early Roman building techniques (Cifani 1995, 185-226) and of the origins of Roman villas (cf. Terrenato 2001), but no

Fig. 2. Plan of the Villa delle Grotte at Grottarossa (after Stefani 1946).

Fig. 3. Plan of the *cuniculi* beneath the Villa delle Grotte (after Stefani 1946).

Fig. 4. Section of the ogive cistern at the Villa delle Grotte (after Cozza 1948).

real effort has been made to study the site at first hand and recent reviews seem to follow passively the received wisdom about early villas. I will review the older evidence, complemented by some recent fieldwork, to propose a new interpretation and chronology for this site.

Fieldwork conducted in 2002-3

In 2002, an attempt was made to determine if any remains of the Villa delle Grotte were still

Fig. 5. Fieldwork (2002) at the Villa delle Grotte (J. A. Becker).

in existence and to ascertain whether a chronological framework for the villa could be established (fig. 5). Even the location of the villa on the ground was not well known, but ruins were discovered *in situ* on the Monte delle Grotte, on the margin of the Via Flaminia just west of the Tiber. Despite heavy vegetation, a number of rooms were identified and documented, all situated along the cliff face documented by Cozza. The identification of these rooms and the realization that the quarry destruction had advanced no further than it had in the 1940s gave reason to hope that more of the villa's ruins were also latent atop the bluff. From the rooms that were observed, some of the building materials (*tufo lionato* and *cappellaccio*) could be determined, on which basis one could begin to establish a chronology for the site.

In 2003, the team returned to the site with the intention of clearing vegetation in order to expose more portions of the villa. Several days of toil yielded few results, as no additional walls were identified. Although the Monte delle Grotte is now included in a protected area associated with the Parco di Veio, it seems that, at some point between Cozza's fieldwork in the 1940s and the present day, a systematic destruction of the villa's ruins occurred. Only additional excavation could determine whether the villa has been totally destroyed, aside from the remains along the cliff face. However, the logistic challenges posed by the instability of the area make any further work there extremely unlikely. At this juncture, further evidence could come only from Stefani's excavation notebooks, now catalogued as part of the *Carte Stefani* in the Biblioteca Apostolica in Vatican City (Buonocore 1988, 213-14).

The site in context

The excavations carried out in 1926 were not scientific in the modern sense; thus, the published report contains no stratigraphic data of any kind, nor is a ceramic chronology offered. A reading of the report provides little more than a decent description of the excavated villa and a well-drawn plan. These facts make it difficult to interpret the site in a number of respects. However, two firm chronological markers help to date the early phases of the villa, as well as to suggest a date for the beginning of its monumental phase. Stefani's report (1946, 55) concluded that the "pre-Roman" phase was constructed in *tufo lionato*,¹ but did not attempt to document the earliest remains in any more detail. Combining his material with data from our analysis of the remains *in situ* can provide important insights. The main building phase can safely be associated with walls constructed in *cappellaccio*. This is the grayish local tufa that also characterizes the earlier phases of the nearby Auditorium site, securely dated on a stratigraphic-

1 In Stefani's report, the local tufa is referred to as *tufo rossiccio*. Here the modern scientific equivalent, *tufo lionato*, will be employed; cf. Montanari and Ammerman 1995, 189-93.

Fig. 6. Photograph of ogive cistern beneath the Basilica Aemilia (after Carettoni 1948).

ic basis (cf. Montanari and Ammerman 1995). This is significant since no above-ground structures in the *Ager Romanus* are known to have been newly built using *cappellaccio* after the Roman sack of Veii in 396 B.C. (Cifani 1995, 199-200). Further, in the 6th c. B.C. the buildings in the centre of Rome that were constructed in *cappellaccio* were the most important structures in the city; they include the podium of the Temple of Iuppiter Optimus Maximus. On the basis of building techniques, then, it is possible to associate the Villa delle Grotte with élite structures of the fledgling Rome.

The archaeological evidence for the Villa delle Grotte is far from comprehensive, however. Since stratigraphic data is not available, we must look elsewhere in the environs of Rome for comparanda that help place the Villa delle Grotte in time. The recent excavations conducted on the Palatine provide an interesting indication. The sequence of masonry evident from those excavations (Carandini and Carafa 1995) helps to confirm my suggested chronology for the Villa delle Grotte. While the interpretation of the Palatine findings is not of concern to us here, the fact that the sequence of building materials moves from local tufa to *cappellaccio*, as at Grottarossa, is more than a coincidence. On the Palatine there is a clear progression from early 6th-c. walls built in *tufa lionato* to late 6th- and early 5th-c. walls built in *cappellaccio*, dated on the basis of associated pottery. The Palatine evidence is much more than a simple analogue for Grottarossa: it serves to confirm the uniformity of élite building practices at Rome at the end of the Archaic period and in the early years of the Republic. The system of cistern and *cuniculi* at Grottarossa examined by Cozza was also built in *cappellaccio* and it too finds a parallel on the Palatine and another in the Forum Romanum beneath the Basilica Aemilia (Carettoni 1948) (fig. 6).² In the case of the cistern, not only does the *cappellaccio* provide a chronological

2 The cistern beneath the Basilica Aemilia is closest in terms of vault structure, with a steep conical profile (Carettoni 1948, 117-19). The inner sides of the blocks are oblique and form a straight line. The cisterns on the Palatine, on the other hand, are well-dated stratigraphically to the late 6th c. B.C. (Pensabene *et al.* 1995, 455-64; Tagliamonte 1999, 18-20); they are also associated with a system of *cuniculi* that is very similar to the one found at Grottarossa (Gjerstad 1953, 104-21).

Fig. 7. Architectural terracotta from the Villa delle Grotte (after Stefani 1946).

Fig. 8. Architectural terracotta no. 23g from the Portonaccio sanctuary at Veii (after Stefani 1953).

indication, but the building technique using round corbel vaults of this type is known only for the pre-Hellenistic period in Italy (later they are replaced by true vaults). This evidence supports the chronology proposed here for the Villa delle Grotte.

Other evidence from Grottarossa supports the presence of an élite residence as early as the late 6th/early 5th c. One piece of evidence is the discovery of an architectural terracotta, a fragment of an eaves tile with a painted geometric decoration in black, red and white (fig. 7). The lower fascia consists of an interlocking, T-shaped meander pattern, which can be compared, for instance, with an example discovered in the Portonaccio sanctuary at Veii (Stefani 1953, 47-48) (fig. 8). The upper fascia is a common chevron motif, while the edge is decorated with a dentilated pattern of the kind found again at Veii (Stefani 1953, 48-49). Other comparable pieces have been found in Rome: they include an eaves tile from the precinct of the Temple of Victory on the Palatine (Pensabene 1988, 57 figs. 3-4), and other examples from the Forum Romanum (Andrén 1939, vol. I, 334; vol. II, pl. 106, no. 378; Gjerstad 1953, vol. III, 83, fig. 53.1-2). All of these are well dated between the very end of the 6th c. and the mid-5th c. B.C., and a similar date can be attributed to the Grottarossa tile (Carlucci, pers. comm.).

“Second phase” terracottas such as those mentioned above have been found almost exclusively in association with sacral contexts, in contrast with those of the 6th c. which are well attested in palaces and élite residences. Yet our knowledge of Early Republican domestic architecture remains very limited, while the presence of painted tiles in private houses (and especially around the atrium where the Auditorium terracotta was found) can in any event be hypothesized, even if the large figural elements were, at this point, reserved for temples (Carlucci, pers. comm.). Even if the association between the painted terracotta and the main building at Grottarossa is not proven stratigraphically, it remains the most likely possibility, given the association of these pieces with *cappellaccio* structures elsewhere in Rome. And the presence of a terracotta in this period is an indisputable sign of élite presence.

The Villa delle Grotte finds other peer sites in the archaeological record. Foremost is the villa at the Auditorium site, excavated in the 1990s.³ This remarkable villa was built in a number of phases, as was Grottarossa, and is again located near the via Flaminia and the Tiber, some 6 km from the centre of Rome. The final interpretations of the site are not yet publicly available, but preliminary reports document 6 phases, with a chronology that runs from the mid-6th c. B.C. to the 2nd c. A.D. (Carandini *et al.* 1997, 117-48). As both architecture and artifacts attest, the Auditorium site was evidently the seat of an important family. Domestic production is also present, another feature in common with the Villa delle Grotte, the *pars rustica* of which contains a number of hollowed industrial-size stone vats. Both villas are large: the original phase at Grottarossa is modest in area, estimated at 300 m² (Cifani 1998). The subsequent double-atrium phase increases the size to over 800 m². The Auditorium site is of similar scale, with the initial phases covering 300 m² and later phases encompassing some 1000 m². The monumental size of these two villas is without parallel in Rome’s immediate vicinity in this

3 Recent interpretations of the Auditorium site favour a ritual function for the building, possibly connected with a recently discovered shrine of Anna Perenna on the Parioli hills (Piranomonte 2002). At present this hypothesis seems to have little to support it.

Fig. 9. Plan of the villa at Selvasecca di Blera (after Berggren and Andrén 1969).

period: one must look to the structure at Poggio Civitate to find anything dating to the 6th c. B.C. of this magnitude (Gros 1996, vol. 2, 272; Terrenato 2001, 15; Turfa and Steinmayer 2002).

The building of the initial phase of the Auditorium site is situated around an open courtyard that would later become the atrium of the villa. Early on, rooms lined three sides of the courtyard. While the preservation of the initial phase of the Villa delle Grotte is not sufficient to allow any discussion of the presence of a central courtyard, the subsequent monumental phase involves atrium architecture but, curiously, there are two *atria* instead of one. In the NE area of the villa is a small Tuscan atrium, complete with an *impluvium* and a system of drainage; this room is organized along the accepted norms for such an atrium, including *alae* and a *tablinum* in its plan, with evidence of renovation and redecoration in the Late Republic. At the opposite side of the villa is another atrium, this one a large tetrastyle room. It is possible that in their present form the two *atria* may represent modifications of the original design, as occurred at the Auditorium site. The presence of sub-phases in the Grottarossa sequence cannot be excluded and is indeed probable, but, given the information available, they are impossible to reconstruct.

Whatever rationale informs the design of the monumental phase of the Villa delle Grotte, its grandiosity and status cannot be disputed. Its imposing position, monumental size, innovative plan, and evidence for domestic industry suggest that, like the Auditorium site, it was probably the suburban residence of a powerful early *gens* exercising regional control between the spheres of Veii and Rome. The geography, close to the territory of Veii, calls to mind the Fabii who launched a private familial war against the Etruscan city in 476 B.C. (Messineo 1991, 86); but no evidence survives to identify the villa's occupants, nor do any texts refer to it.

Other sites in the hinterland of Rome may be peers for the Middle Republican phase of the Villa delle Grotte. One is a villa with an apparent double-atrium plan excavated at Casale Ghella in the 1980s (Messineo *et al.* 1985, 177-84). It also possessed an elaborate cistern and *cuniculus* system, but overall it is poorly preserved. Another possible peer (also in need of systematic re-analysis) is Selvasecca di Blera (fig. 9). That site was excavated in the 1960s by the Swedish Institute in Rome but has never been comprehensively published.⁴ It is often cited as

⁴ Berggren and Andrén 1969, 51-71: this interim report represents the only substantial publication of the excavation of this important site. The ground-plan, alongside the evidence for Archaic terracottas, suggests that the villa at Blera may be a peer of Auditorium II and Grottarossa II. Further work on the

belonging to the 2nd c. B.C., with Carandini (1989, 162) going so far as to label it the “first villa” in Italy. Evidence for the production of architectural terracottas of late Archaic mien, however, suggests that the villa’s earliest phase is more likely to be dated to the 5th c. B.C.

Conclusions

An early date for the first two phases of the Villa delle Grotte would seem to have considerable implications for several key issues in the archaeology of Republican Italy, but several recent contributions have questioned precisely this aspect of N. Terrenato’s reconstruction. It goes without saying that pottery evidence from a clear stratigraphic sequence is the only kind of data that would put all doubts to rest, but this is not likely to be forthcoming in the near term. The chronology cannot rely on the date of floors that could have been added at any time during the long occupation of the site.⁵ And while we are all aware of the inherent problems of dates based on sequences of building techniques, the case of *cappellaccio* deserves special attention: it is a rather poor construction material that is completely abandoned as soon as better tufts are available. The combination of *cappellaccio* blocks, ashlar masonry, an ogive cistern, and “Second phase” architectural terracottas make a date in the 2nd or even the 3rd c. B.C. almost untenable.

If a date in the 5th or 4th c. is accepted, especially in view of the Auditorium and Palatine sequences, as most likely for at least a part of the main building, a number of ramifications follow. First, the early appearance of élite residences in Central Italy would be supported: at this point, it appears to become an archaeological phenomenon which can be explained in different ways, but which can no longer be ignored.⁶ Since at both the Auditorium site and Grottarossa early residences developed into classic Late Republican villas, it is hard to deny that they represent a major influence in the formulation of this architectural type, as is accepted by scholars such as P. Gros (1996, vol. 2, 271-72). On the other hand, the Hellenistic connection seems to become more tenuous and contrived with the progress of research.

When the number of villas exploded in the Late Republic, they derived some of their basic concepts from the few élite ‘palaces’ that had been in existence for centuries. The precise timing of this boom in villas is another hotly debated topic, but it does not directly affect the argument here. Even if one believes in a “Catonian” date for the diffusion of villas, Grottarossa and the Auditorium site retain their ‘seniority’ by at least a century. In any case, it must be said that the supporters of the high chronology have so far failed to turn up villas in any numbers that were first built as massive residences between c.350 and 120 B.C.:⁷ the bulk of the villas seem to date to the Sullan or Caesarian period, at the earliest. A reconsideration of this kind would advance further the case for indigenous origins, given that the essentials of classic Roman architecture were all firmly in place by 50 B.C.

Virtually all of the questions raised here are far from settled. But this in itself is an improvement over the confident generalizations made over recent decades. The issue of the origins of Roman villas has been thrown wide open. It may be hoped that the Villa delle Grotte will

terracottas from the site is now being carried out by M. Söderlind (Lund University), while a volume by J. W. Hayes on the pottery is forthcoming (it will include a summary of the architecture by A. Klynne).

- 5 Fentress 2003, 553-56. It is surprising to see a veteran excavator use such an inconclusive argument to propose a more recent date for the villa. It is also odd that she reacts so vehemently to an early date for Grottarossa, when in any case one is firmly established for the Auditorium site. The real issue is the virtual absence of new, Middle Republican villas, but Fentress fails to add anything new to this contentious problem (the same can be said of the summary assessment in Carandini and Cambi 2002, 12).
- 6 Even studies of villas in Central Italy published quite recently (e.g., Lafon 2001; Romizzi 2001; De Franceschini 2005) perpetuate the long-held, but largely untested, view that correlates the genesis of the classic villa form with Roman expansion. In this context they overlook any archaeological evidence that does not conform to an argument for a Late Republican chronology of sites such as Villa delle Grotte.
- 7 Important new data has been published for a site at Centocelle: Gioia *et al.* 2004. For fuller discussion of the problem of villas in the 3rd c. B.C., see Terrenato and Becker forthcoming.

figure prominently in future discussions of this topic. We may be reaching the point where the wider implications of what Mottini and Stefani found long ago in a quarry-face on the via Flaminia should be considered.

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